

Project StoryMachine: Spatial Hypertext as a Tool for Contemporary, Transcultural Folkloristics

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ducted jointly by six research groups in Germany and the UK, which is developing an innovative digital infrastructure to preserve, explore, and democratize access to folklore traditions and vernacular storytelling practices around the world, with emphasis on German- and English-speaking communities. Recognizing folklore as a cornerstone of shared cultural identity, the project addresses critical challenges in archival practices, and particularly the lack of interactive, dynamic, accessible and inclusive tools for exploring both traditional and emerging folk narratives. Existing approaches to digital folklore archiving remain largely static, focusing on isolated collections without fostering meaningful exploration, collaboration, or analysis. *StoryMachine* redefines these paradigms by integrating spatial hypertext and recommender systems to create a visually dynamic, user-centered interface.

Aligning with Harvilahti's (2022) call for motif indexes to evolve beyond typological rigidity, this project aims to integrate folkloristic databases, multimedia texts and catalogues like the Aarne-Thompson-Uther Index (Uther, 2024) alongside ethnographically collected data into SPORE, a newly developed AI-augmented platform based on the principles and cognitive workings of spatial hypertext (see Fig. 1) (Roßner et al., 2023; Atzenbeck and Nürnberg, 2019). Hypertext and narrative share intertwined histories. More than a compositional framework, hypertext as a networked textual infrastructure offers a powerful philosophical approach to structuring and presenting knowledge integrating alternative, multilinear options of organizing and envisioning content (Ensslin, 2007). However, our starting point is the fact that node-link is not the only type of hypertext structure, nor is it the most appropriate for expressing ideas or working creatively (Anderson and Millard, 2023), with document-centered systems such as the Web lacking maps that provide an overview of the overall conceptual structure of relationships.

As early as the 1990s, researchers started developing spatial hypertext systems (Marshall et al., 1991; Shipman et al., 2002), which represent associations between units of information placed in a (usually 2D) space by their orientation, spatial distance or visual appearance (e.g. color, shape or size). Further advancing this idea, *StoryMachine* facilitates the comparison of motifs, variations, and shared patterns across cultural and geographic contexts. Beyond mere cataloging, it fosters collaboration between users and AI, leveraging machine intelligence to co-create and dynamically link stories while empowering human participants to shape outcomes. By critically engaging with motif analysis, digital storytelling practices, and the psychological dimensions of interactivity, the project introduces a co-creative, emergent model for exploring folklore traditions from orally transmitted fairytales through popular media fiction, algorithmic folklore and meme culture (de Seta, 2024).

This paper introduces *StoryMachine* (AHRC/DFG: AT 153/1-1), a transdisciplinary DH project (2025–2028) con-

Figure 1: Early prototype of the user interface on which *StoryMachine* will be based, with color-coded user nodes and white context-matching suggestions. Screenshot taken from Roßner et al. (2023).

From a systems perspective, *StoryMachine* is a Component-based Open Hypermedia System (CB-OHS) that supports multiple structural paradigms, including spatially represented knowledge structures. It is organized into three layers: user interface, structure services, and knowledge services (Atzenbeck et al., 2018). The structure services layer comprises “spatio-temporal parsers” that analyze users’ spatially constructed knowledge, enabling the system to approximate their interpretations (Schedel and Atzenbeck, 2016). On this basis, the system queries underlying knowledge bases to retrieve suggestions that are contextually relevant. These knowledge bases are constructed using techniques from AI and natural language processing (NLP) and are internally represented as graphs. Additionally, user-generated knowledge articulated in the 2D workspace and interpreted by parsers is stored in dedicated knowledge bases, ensuring that it can subsequently be surfaced as contextually appropriate suggestions for others’ work. Recent publications demonstrate how this infrastructure is employed in the context of storytelling (Atzenbeck et al., 2023; Roßner et al., 2023).

StoryMachine follows a multi-pronged, iterative development process involving its target communities of teachers, teacher-trainees, creative practitioners, cultural heritage professionals and wider publics in the platform design from the outset, committing to the multimodal and participatory ethos of contemporary digital scholarship (Tolbert & Johnson 2019). Early pilot studies combined user observation with semi-structured interviews and content analysis of think-aloud protocols. Preliminary results have encouraged improvements to the prototype’s navigation and usability, revealing the system’s potential as a platform for playful interpretation of multiple story variations, while also raising questions about representational models.

The project also confronts pressing issues regarding authorship and ownership in generative AI, advocating for a context-sensitive, co-creative approach that reimagines human-machine partnerships and promotes awareness of data literacy and epistemic agency. With implications for storytelling, pedagogy, digital heritage, museology and creative writing, *StoryMachine* exemplifies the possibilities of AI-driven hypertext systems to reshape transcultural digital

folkloristics, offering new paradigms for knowledge exploration and cultural exchange.

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